

Analysis of the Effectiveness of Implementing Fingerprint Attendance on the Discipline of ASN and NON ASN Employees in the Pondokgede District Education Service Unit

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ABSTRACT

The development of the times is increasingly advanced so that it also has an impact on technological progress. The system that was previously manual has now become electronic, such as the implementation of fingerprint attendance. This research aims to determine the effectiveness of using Attendance fingerprints regarding the discipline of ASN and non-ASN employees in the Pondokgede District Education Service Unit under the Bekasi City Education Service. This research is descriptive qualitative research, the data source utilizes primary data and data collection through interviews with informants. The interview results were analyzed using the listening method and note-taking method. Results of research on the effectiveness of using Attendance fingerprints The discipline of ASN and non-ASN employees in the Pondokgede District Education Service Unit is measured through indicators measuring program effectiveness including target achievement, adaptability, job satisfaction and responsibility. Based on target achievement, where the implementation of fingerprint attendance is a government target that has been well realized and when implemented in the Pondokgede District Education Service Unit had a quite good impact on improving employee discipline and performance.

INTRODUCTION

In the current era of globalization, organizational institutions or agencies must be able to adapt to technological advances. Technological advances have resulted in a change process from manual to electronic systems. Technology is able to replace manual management systems in an organization or company, such as attendance which was previously manual now uses an electronic system. The need for fast and accurate information and communication is very necessary to provide original (real) data, especially in an institution or agency. By creating sophisticated tools, an institution or agency can help, obtain, control and process all data access easily. So that the use of information technology will help institutions or agencies in supporting decision making regarding the problems being faced. Apart from that, the use of information technology can also ensure good governance. According to (Muslikhah, 2019), to support the creation of good governance, managing employee data requires the application of technology and information systems. The impact on institutions or agencies that use technology and information systems in managing employee data is the availability of actual and accurate information so that decision making can be carried out efficiently and can increase public trust. The use of fingerprints as a tool to control attendance levels has been widely used in various government and private agencies as well as companies to create security. When employees use fingerprints as an attendance tool, the employee cannot falsify their attendance data. This is because one person's fingerprints are identical and will be different from those of another person (Khairuman, 2022). According to (Heriawanto, 2004), the implementation of manually filling in the attendance or attendance register (only in the form of an attendance register book), will create an obstacle for the organization to monitor employee discipline in terms of punctuality of arrival and departure times for employees every day.

According to (Ni Luh Tesi Riani, 2017), Human resources (HR) are one of the most important factors in a company that determines the success or failure of a company. Therefore, human resources must be managed well to increase organizational effectiveness and efficiency.

According to (Drever, 1952) From a psychological perspective, discipline is the ability to control behavior that comes from within a person in accordance with things that have been regulated from outside or existing norms. In other words, discipline from a psychological perspective is a person's behavior that appears and is able to adapt to the rules that have been set. In responding to employee discipline problems, the Bekasi City government continues to strive to carry out bureaucratic reform to improve employee discipline. These efforts include implementing a fingerprint attendance system. which is intended to ensure that the attendance data obtained for Civil Servants and Contract Workers (Non ASN) is more accurate and at the same time ensure that employee attendance discipline increases and is well monitored.

Referring to the background above, researchers are interested in Analyzing the Effectiveness of Implementing Fingerprint Attendance on the Discipline of ASN and NON ASN Employees in the Pondokgede District Education Service Unit.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Milleri in (Tangkilisan, 2005), effectiveness is the degree to which a social system achieves its goals, while efficiency is the comparison between costs and results, so that effectiveness is directly linked to the achievement of a goal. Criteria or indicators of effectiveness according to (Tangkilisan, 2005) namely: 1. Target Achievement, meaning the extent to which the target can be realized well. This can be seen from the extent to which the organization's goals are implemented in achieving targets in accordance with the goals that have been set, 2. Adaptability (Flexibility), meaning that the success of the organization is seen from the extent to which the organization can adapt to changes that occur both from within the organization and outside the organization, 3. Job satisfaction, a condition felt by all members of the organization who are able to provide. Comfort and motivation for improving organizational performance. The focus of this element is between work and the suitability of the rewards or system applied to members of the organization who excel and have done work exceeding the existing workload, 4. Responsibility, the organization can carry out the responsibilities it has assumed in accordance with the provisions that have been made previously and can face and resolve problems that occur with their work. If the goals and objectives have been achieved in accordance with the plan, it can be said to be effective. If these goals and objectives are not completed within the specified time, then it can be said to be ineffective. Thus, what is meant by effectiveness is how far the level of balance of a social system is towards achieving goals and utilizing human energy.

(James L. Gibson, 2006) conclude the criteria for the effectiveness of an organization in 5 (five) indicators, namely as follows:

1. Production, describes the organization's ability to produce the quantity and quality of output in accordance with environmental demand, this measure is directly related to the output consumed by the organization's customers,
2. Efficiency, as a comparison number between output and input, a comparison between profits and costs or with output over time is a general form and measure of this,
3. Job satisfaction and morale, shows to what extent the organization meets the needs of employees and society,
4. Adaptability, to what extent the organization can respond to internal and external changes. This criterion relates to management's ability to predict changes in the environment and within the organization itself.
5. Development, the usual development efforts are training or outreach programs for management staff or the community and non-management. But now organizational development has become more varied and includes a number of psychological and sociological approaches.

Attendance is an activity or routine carried out by employees to prove that they are present or absent from work at an agency Erna, 2012 in (Risfa Fadila, 2019). This absence is related to the application of discipline determined by each agency. One application of technology to achieve the goal of improving employee discipline is by implementing fingerprint attendance at an agency.

According to Moch Tofik, 2010 in(Risfa Fadila, 2019)explained that fingerprint is a technology that supports attendance needs, which includes entry, storing data on entry and departure times, processing this data into a report which can later be used to make policies carried out by the leadership.

Work discipline according to(Simamora, 2005)Discipline is a form of employee self-control and regular implementation shows the level of seriousness of the work team in an organization. Meanwhile, according to(Helmi, 1996)in(Safudin, 2018)explains that work discipline is an attitude and behavior that intends to obey all organizational regulations based on one's own awareness of adapting to organizational regulations.

According to(Robbins, 2015)There are three indicators of work discipline:

1. Time Discipline Time discipline is defined as an attitude or behavior that shows compliance with working hours, which includes employee attendance and compliance during working hours, employees carrying out tasks on time and correctly
2. Regulatory Discipline Rules and regulations written and unwritten ones are made so that the goals of an organization can be achieved well. This requires a loyal attitude from employees towards the commitments that have been set. Loyalty here means being obedient and obedient in carrying out orders from superiors and the rules and regulations that have been established, as well as employee obedience in wearing the uniforms that have been determined by the company organization.
3. Responsible Discipline One form of employee responsibility is the best use and maintenance of equipment so that it can support office or production activities running smoothly. As well as the ability to face work that is your responsibility as an employee, such as maintaining productivity because this productivity is of course closely related to efforts to work effectively and efficiently, apart from that it is also carried out in order to meet the targets given by the company, Maintaining Production Quality to ensure that the quality of the production in accordance with company standards.

Working hours on weekdays are regulated as follows(Bekasi PW, 2017):

- a. Monday to Thursday:
 1. come to work: 07.30 WIB;
 2. rest: 12.00-13.00 WIB; And
 3. leave work: 16.00 WIB.
- b. Friday:
 1. come to work: 07.30 WIB;
 2. sports: 07.30-08.00 WIB;
 3. rest: 11.45-12.45 WIB; And
 4. leave work: 16.00 WIB.

METHODOLOGY

This research is descriptive qualitative research. This research was carried out in the Education Services Unit Subdistrict Pondokgede which will take place from June 2023 to August 2023. The technique for collecting data is interviews by asking questions to the Coordinator, application operator, and employees within the Education service unit. Subdistrict Pondokgede This research uses primary data, namely data obtained directly by researchers

through interviews. The data sources obtained came from informants and data from the employee attendance website when researching. This research is located in the Education Services Unit Subdistrict Pondokgede is under the scope of the Bekasi City Education Office, the population used is ASN and Non ASN in the Education Service Unit Subdistrict Pondokgede. The samples taken by researchers were employees in the Education Services Unit work environment Subdistrict Pondokgede. So the total sample involved was 16 people consisting of 5 ASN people and 11 non-ASN people.

The data collection process in this research is as follows:

- a. Ask questions to informants and listen to and record answers from informants
- b. Carry out data reduction, abstraction, transformation and assessment.

Framework of thinking

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The Effectiveness of Implementing Fingerprint Attendance on the Discipline of ASN and NON ASN Employees in the Pondokgede District Education Service Unit

To improve the work discipline of ASN and Non-ASN in the Pondokgede District Education Service Unit, it can be seen from several indicators of effectiveness according to theory (Tangkilisan, 2005) as follows:

1. Target Achievement

Regarding achieving the target of implementing fingerprint attendance, it really has a big influence on the employees here, apart from that, making attendance reports is much easier because it is directly recorded in the attendance application so there will be no manipulation.

Attendance is an activity or routine carried out by employees to prove that they are present or absent from work at an agency Erna, 2012 in (Risfa Fadila, 2019).

The image shows a screenshot of a fingerprint attendance recording system. The interface displays a list of employees with columns for their names, positions, and attendance status. The data is organized in a table format, with rows representing individual employees and columns representing different attendance metrics. The system appears to be a web-based application used for tracking employee presence.

Figure 1. Recording

Source:(Attendance Bekasi City, 2023)

Target achievement in implementing fingerprint attendance has been well realized and implementing fingerprint attendance has turned out to be very effective in terms of improving the discipline and performance of Civil Servants (ASN) and Contract Work Personnel (Non ASN) in the Pondokgede District Education Service Unit. With fingerprint attendance, it makes the process of making reports easier because it is immediately recorded when employees in the Pondokgede District Education Service Unit come and go home, so that if an employee is late or absent there will be a penalty, and this is stated in the Bekasi Mayor's Regulations. No. 24 of 2022 concerning Additional Income for Civil Servants and Prospective Civil Servants and Bekasi Mayor Regulation No. 73 of 2021 Fourth Amendment to the Bekasi Mayor's regulation concerning Guidelines for Providing Income for Work Contract Workers within the Bekasi City Government.

2. Adaptability

The ability to adapt in implementing fingerprint attendance in the Pondokgede District Education Service Unit experienced difficulties at the start of its use because some employees in the Pondokgede District Education Service Unit were not able to adapt to arriving and leaving on time. And for now, overall, employees have been able to adapt well, even though network disruptions sometimes occur, there is a solution provided, namely the operator at the Pondokgede District Education Services Unit makes a rebuttal letter by attaching fingerprint and Web3 attendance as proof and then takes it to the Bekasi City Education Service operator for repaired. And the presence of this fingerprint is very easy and comfortable to use compared to what used to be done manually.

No	ID	Nama	Umur	Gol	Jen	Gaji	L3	Gaji	Status
2023-06-01	11	327501120001001	37:11:30	10:00:40					Full
2023-06-08	11	327501120001001	37:13:10	10:00:50					Full
2023-06-15	11	327501120001001	37:22:11	10:07:00					Full
2023-06-22	11	327501120001001	37:17:40	10:00:10					Full
2023-06-29	11	327501120001001	37:20:03	10:00:30					Full
2023-07-06	11	327501120001001	37:11:00	10:00:10					Full
2023-07-13	11	327501120001001	37:07:27	10:07:37					Full
2023-07-20	11	327501120001001	37:10:45	10:21:40	07:23:10	10:00:10			Full
2023-07-27	11	327501120001001	37:13:31	10:00:10					Full
2023-08-03	11	327501120001001	37:11:40	10:00:10					Full
2023-08-10	11	327501120001001	37:20:30	10:00:40					Full
2023-08-17	11	327501120001001	37:22:47	10:00:40					Full
2023-08-24	11	327501120001001	37:15:00	10:00:10					Full
2023-08-31	11	327501120001001	37:08:41	10:07:00					Full
2023-09-07	11	327501120001001	37:24:11	10:07:30					Full
2023-09-14	11	327501120001001	37:11:30	10:00:10					Full
2023-09-21	11	327501120001001	37:22:00	10:00:10					Full

Figure. 2

Source:(Web 3, 2023)

3. Job satisfaction

Job satisfaction is one of the most important points in an agency which plays an important role in determining the achievement of results in accordance with the objectives that have been carried out. Like the implementation of fingerprint attendance which aims to improve ASN and Non-ASN discipline in the Pondogede District Education Service Unit which provides job satisfaction for employees, where if employees follow predetermined regulations such as discipline in attendance then ASN and Non-ASN discipline in the District Education Service Unit Pondogede will receive TPP (Additional Employee Income) according to the workload, work performance, working conditions, professional scarcity of each employee and TKK (Non ASN) will receive income according to the position of each employee.

4. Responsibility

Every ASN and non-ASN employee in the Pondogede District Education Services Unit has their own responsibilities both in terms of attendance and in terms of performance because if they are not carried out in accordance with predetermined regulations there will be consequences that must be borne by ASN and non-ASN employees in the Unit. Pondogede District Education Services, namely TPP cuts for ASN and salary/income cuts in accordance with Bekasi Mayor Regulation No. 24 of 2022 concerning Additional Income for Civil Servants and Prospective Civil Servants and Bekasi Mayor Regulation No. 73 of 2021 Fourth Amendment to regulations Mayor of Bekasi regarding Guidelines for Providing Income for Employment Contract Workers within the Bekasi City Government.

The impact of implementing fingerprint attendance. The impact of implementing fingerprint attendance for ASN and non-ASN employees in the Pondogede District Education Service Unit is as follows:

1. Fingerprint attendance can increase employee productivity

During the implementation of fingerprint attendance in the Ponggede District Education Service Unit, it gave two impacts, namely good impacts. The good impact after implementing fingerprint attendance is increasing the productivity of ASN and non-ASN employees in the Ponggede District Education Service Unit, both in terms of attendance and performance.

2. Fingerprint attendance can motivate employees

The implementation of fingerprint attendance has had a big influence on ASN and non-ASN employees in the Ponggede District Education Service Unit in increasing motivation. To increase employee motivation there must be responsibility for each employee, namely attendance and performance because these two components are closely related to the TPP for ASN and the salary/income for non-ASN that will be obtained by

CONCLUSIONS

In this research regarding the Effectiveness of Implementing Fingerprint Attendance on the Discipline of ASN and NON ASN Employees in the Ponggede District Education Service Unit, it can be described with several conclusions as follows:

1. At the beginning of the implementation of fingerprint attendance in 2017 there were difficulties, because there were still many disruptions in the form of operating finger print machines, networks, and operator staff were still in the learning process. And if you look at the effectiveness indicators according to Tangkilisan (2005: 138) based on research results, it shows that: first, target achievement, where the implementation of fingerprint attendance is a government target that has been well realized and when implemented in the Ponggede District Education Service Unit, it has had quite an impact. good for improving employee discipline and performance. Second, the ability to adapt, at the beginning of implementation there were problems, one of the factors was that employees had not adapted to the on-time arrival and departure times according to the rules given by the Mayor of Bekasi. Third, job satisfaction, when fingerprint attendance was implemented, increased, which was supported by no TPP (Additional Employee Income) deductions for ASN and no salary/income deductions for Non-ASN if they attended and worked optimally. Fourth responsibility, since the implementation of fingerprint attendance, ASN and non-ASN employees in the Ponggede District Education Services Unit are quite good because they have their respective responsibilities both in terms of attendance and reporting the results of their performance.
2. The impact of implementing fingerprint attendance for ASN and non-ASN employees in the Ponggede District Education Services Unit is: fingerprint attendance can increase employee productivity. The research results explain that it has a good impact, where the impact is good after implementing fingerprint attendance for ASN and non-ASN employees. in the Ponggede District Education Services Unit, employee productivity has increased.

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